

FEATURES OF INTERNAL RATING IN COMMERCIAL BANKS

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Abstract. This article describes the necessity and features of determining the rating of commercial banks. Also, the prospects of introducing an internal rating in the process of determining the rating of banks are mentioned.

Key words: commercial banks, rating, bank rating, internal rating, Basel Committee, profit, profitability, asset, capital.

Determining the rating of commercial banks and announcing it is very important for bank customers and investors. The ratings provide the bank's interested parties with generalized information on its future development processes or possible problems. Ratings are determined on the basis of financial indicators monitored by management bodies and studied by rating agencies, as well as future strategies of the bank, as well as experts' conclusions. Ratings are an opportunity to seek solutions to possible negative processes in advance in order to ensure the financial stability of banks. Banks with high ratings are an important tool for accessing international markets and attracting investment.

A higher rating of banks is implemented directly by strengthening internal ratings. Internal ratings play an important role in improving financial and operational activities of banks, risk management, and strengthening corporate governance. In international practice, internal rating system models provide an opportunity to take into account the borrower's credit risk as a financial information institution and assess credit risk based on financial instruments. At the same time, it should be noted that the requirement to determine the internal credit rating of commercial banks is reflected in the requirements of the Basel Committee

on International Banking Supervision, and today it is widely used in the practice of commercial banks of most developed countries¹.

It should be noted that the internal rating system evaluates the credit risk of banks, determines the parameters of bank capital adequacy and stress-testing and helps in their comprehensive assessment.

In the internal rating, the customer's points are summarized based on quantitative and qualitative indicators, and the final rating of borrowers is determined.

When determining the internal rating of banks' customers, statistical data is analyzed from various sources, namely, internal and external data on the customer's default, as well as quantitative and qualitative indicators of the customer's rating.

Based on the above, we would like to make the following scientific and practical suggestions regarding the use of the internal rating model by local commercial banks in their activities:

1. Recently, various problems have appeared in the credit portfolio of commercial banks of our country, that is, the weight of problematic assets is increasing, as a result of banks not paying serious attention to these issues, and as a result of the inability of customers to repay loans, chain problems are arising. Therefore, it is appropriate for commercial banks to develop an internal rating model and to continuously monitor the financial situation of borrowers and implement it in practice.

2. Taking into account that each commercial bank independently develops credit policies, develop criteria for evaluating the quantity and quality indicators of borrowers and continuously improve them based on the economic situation.

3. To update the ratings of the bank's borrowers, that is, its customers, every month, to study their proposals for providing financial services to customers

¹ www.bis.org - Official website of the Bank for International Settlements

with high ratings, to serve them on the basis of the rule that all services are for customers.

In conclusion, the internal rating system of commercial banks and its wide application in banks will give effective results and serve to improve the general rating of commercial banks and increase and strengthen the reputation of banks in the banking market in the future.

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